

Multichronicity in the Italian Regions

It decreased on average in the Italian regions as well in the gap between North and South.

ISTAT-BES calculates the value of multichronicity and serious limitations defined as the percentage of people aged 75 and over who declare to be suffering from 3 or more chronic diseases and / or to have serious limitations, for at least 6 months, due to health problems in carrying out the activities that people usually carry out. These data are available between 2008 and 2020.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of multichronicity and severe limitations in 2020.

Campania is in first place for the value of multichronicity and serious limitations in 2020 with an amount equal to 62.1 units, followed by Sardinia with a value equal to 62, and by Sicily with an amount equal to 60.6 units. In the middle of the table there are Puglia with an amount equal to 47.8 units, followed by Friuli Venezia Giulia with an amount equal to 47.6 units, and by Lombardy with an amount equal to 46.5. Molise closes the ranking with a value of 37.6, followed by Trentino Alto Adige with a value of 33.6 units and Valle d'Aosta with a value of 29.9 units. On average, the value of the percentage of people suffering from multichronicity and severe limitations is equal to an amount of 48.07.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage variation of multichronicity and severe limitations between 2008 and 2020.

Piedmont is in first place for the percentage change in multichronicity and severe limitations with a value of 17.77% or equal to a value of 7 units, followed by Sardinia with an amount equal to 17.42% or equal to a amount of 9.2 units and from Friuli-Venezia Giulia with an amount equal to 11.21% equal to an amount of 4.8 units. In the middle of the table there are Umbria with a value equal to -4.1% equal to an amount of -2.4 units, followed by Calabria with a value equal to -6.44% equal to an amount of -3, 9 units, and from Veneto with an amount equal to -12.39% equal to an amount of -5.6 units. Puglia closes the ranking with an amount equal to a value of -22.4% equal to an amount of -13.8 units, followed by Valle d'Aosta with an amount equal to -26.35% equal to an amount of -10.7 units and from Molise with a value equal to -32.25% equal to an amount of -17.9 units. Overall and on average for the regions considered, the value of multichronicity and serious limitations decreased from an amount of 52.50 units up to a value of 48.08 units or equal to a variation of -4.42 units equal to a value of -8.42%.

Italian macro-regions. The percentage of people over 75 years of age suffering from multichronicity and severe limitations decreased in all Italian macro-regions between 2008 and 2020 except in Northern Italy. In fact, in Northern Italy the percentage of people over 75 suffering from multichronicity and severe limitations has grown from an amount of 44.4 units up to a value of 44.6 units or equal to a variation of 0.2 units equal to a value of 0.45%. In Central Italy the percentage of people with multichronicity and severe limitations decreased from an amount of 52.9 units to a value of 47 units or a variation equal to an amount of -5.9 units equal to a variation of -11, 15%. In the South the percentage of people with multi-chronicity and severe limitations over 75 decreased from an amount of 60.8 units to a value of 56.9 units or equal to a variation of -3.9 units equal to a value of -6, 41%. Overall in Italy the percentage of people with multichronicity and serious limitations decreased between 2008 and 2020 from an amount equal to 51.6 units up to a value of 48.8 units or a reduction equal to an amount of -2.8 units equal to a value of -5.42%. However, it should be

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considered that the percentage of people affected by multichronicity and severe limitations in Southern Italy is higher than the national average by about 8.1 percentage points. It clearly follows that the health conditions of the population over seventy-five in the south tend to be worse than those of the same age in the Center and in the North.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is proposed below. The analysis shows the presence of two clusters as indicated below, namely:

- *Cluster 1:* Sicily, Umbria, Campania, Calabria, Puglia, Abruzzo, Sardinia, Basilicata, Molise, Lazio;
- *Cluster 2:* Piedmont, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Lombardy, Veneto, Trentino-Alto Adige, Tuscany, Valle d'Aosta, Liguria, Emilia-Romagna, Marche.

From the point of view of the ordering of the clusters it is possible to verify that the median value of multichronicity and serious limitations in Cluster 1-C1 is equal to an amount of 55.05 units, while the corresponding value for Cluster 2-C2 is equal to an amount of 44.75 units. The following evidently derives from this ordering $C1 = 55.05 > C2 = 44.75$. That is, the presence of people over 75 years of age with multichronicity in the C1 regions is about 10 percentage points more present than in the C2 regions. From a geographical point of view, the contrast between regions of the Center-South that have high multichronicity values and serious limitations is absolutely evident compared to the regions of the Center-North that have low multichronicity values. This contrast could also reflect a different quality and quantity of regional health services together with elements related to aspects of lifestyle habits.

Conclusions. The percentage of people over 75 suffering from multichronicity and severe limitations has significantly decreased considering the average of the Italian regions between 2008 and 2020. However, there are regions in which this value has increased, namely Piedmont, Sardinia, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Lombardy, Campania, and Sicily. The difference between the Central-Northern and Central-Southern regions is certainly evident in the data. To demonstrate that the income-related aspects and the quality of local health systems have some relevance in determining the health conditions for the over 75. The health dimension of the economic gap between Northern and Southern Italy, which affects that part, therefore appears dramatically. of a particularly fragile population which is made up of the elderly.

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Acknowledgment: I want to thank the colleagues of the Lum Enterprise S.r.l. and prof. Alberto Costantiello and Lucio Laureti of LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro.

Competing interests: The author declares no competing interest.

	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Piemonte	★ 39,40	★ 40,00	★ 43,90	★ 43,80	★ 47,40	★ 50,50	★ 40,90	★ 39,60	★ 42,10	★ 44,00	★ 42,90	★ 40,90	★ 46,40
Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	★ 40,60	★ 39,50	★ 59,20	★ 44,20	★ 34,60	★ 51,20	★ 43,10	★ 46,20	★ 35,10	★ 38,50	★ 40,40	★ 47,30	★ 29,90
Liguria	★ 42,60	★ 47,00	★ 40,90	★ 46,60	★ 49,10	★ 49,90	★ 47,80	★ 46,90	★ 44,50	★ 46,20	★ 55,80	★ 44,80	★ 45,30
Lombardia	★ 43,50	★ 48,80	★ 48,40	★ 49,90	★ 50,10	★ 47,80	★ 47,60	★ 41,30	★ 45,90	★ 48,90	★ 44,70	★ 44,60	★ 46,50
Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	★ 40,70	★ 38,90	★ 42,10	★ 41,50	★ 39,70	★ 40,40	★ 38,70	★ 30,80	★ 35,50	★ 32,20	★ 35,00	★ 34,80	★ 33,60
Veneto	★ 45,20	★ 50,30	★ 46,90	★ 41,20	★ 46,20	★ 52,40	★ 49,90	★ 40,20	★ 46,40	★ 47,40	★ 43,40	★ 40,50	★ 39,60
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	★ 42,80	★ 42,90	★ 46,20	★ 42,30	★ 45,80	★ 42,10	★ 46,70	★ 42,50	★ 39,30	★ 45,70	★ 38,30	★ 45,00	★ 47,60
Emilia-Romagna	★ 52,40	★ 50,70	★ 45,60	★ 49,30	★ 51,90	★ 49,80	★ 44,50	★ 44,30	★ 49,40	★ 43,30	★ 47,80	★ 50,60	★ 45,50
Toscana	★ 45,00	★ 46,80	★ 49,80	★ 55,80	★ 50,60	★ 48,70	★ 42,00	★ 42,20	★ 47,60	★ 43,50	★ 44,80	★ 48,40	★ 43,60
Umbria	★ 58,50	★ 63,20	★ 62,70	★ 53,40	★ 51,30	★ 59,60	★ 59,40	★ 61,70	★ 60,80	★ 61,70	★ 66,30	★ 59,20	★ 56,10
Marche	★ 56,70	★ 55,50	★ 51,80	★ 50,70	★ 41,90	★ 47,00	★ 50,80	★ 46,60	★ 44,90	★ 44,80	★ 48,20	★ 50,90	★ 44,20
Lazio	★ 57,50	★ 53,00	★ 50,90	★ 52,40	★ 52,00	★ 54,00	★ 53,30	★ 55,30	★ 57,50	★ 58,00	★ 53,10	★ 49,00	★ 49,10
Abruzzo	★ 65,10	★ 62,70	★ 54,60	★ 61,40	★ 57,90	★ 51,90	★ 58,30	★ 53,70	★ 61,90	★ 53,40	★ 57,50	★ 53,60	★ 54,00
Molise	★ 55,50	★ 59,50	★ 53,80	★ 61,40	★ 49,30	★ 63,20	★ 47,10	★ 59,40	★ 53,40	★ 47,80	★ 50,80	★ 58,30	★ 37,60
Campania	★ 61,00	★ 55,60	★ 57,80	★ 60,20	★ 63,30	★ 68,60	★ 64,60	★ 58,60	★ 55,10	★ 57,20	★ 63,90	★ 56,40	★ 62,10
Puglia	★ 61,60	★ 58,70	★ 59,00	★ 52,90	★ 62,40	★ 63,60	★ 58,00	★ 56,40	★ 57,70	★ 52,60	★ 54,30	★ 54,10	★ 47,80
Basilicata	★ 67,90	★ 64,30	★ 58,30	★ 57,80	★ 60,20	★ 56,00	★ 46,90	★ 53,00	★ 57,30	★ 63,20	★ 62,70	★ 64,20	★ 53,30
Calabria	★ 60,60	★ 64,60	★ 66,00	★ 65,00	★ 68,10	★ 67,30	★ 71,00	★ 66,80	★ 60,20	★ 65,30	★ 59,80	★ 59,80	★ 56,70
Sicilia	★ 60,50	★ 58,80	★ 57,30	★ 59,50	★ 61,00	★ 61,50	★ 61,80	★ 60,90	★ 62,90	★ 62,10	★ 58,40	★ 62,60	★ 60,60
Sardegna	★ 52,80	★ 65,30	★ 58,80	★ 60,20	★ 54,60	★ 51,70	★ 66,00	★ 54,20	★ 59,40	★ 59,90	★ 62,00	★ 56,50	★ 62,00

2020	Regione	Cluster
46.4	Piemonte	C2
29.9	Valle d'Aosta/V...	C2
45.3	Liguria	C2
46.5	Lombardia	C2
33.6	Trentino-Alto A...	C2
39.6	Veneto	C2
47.6	Friuli-Venezia G...	C2
45.5	Emilia-Romagna	C2
43.6	Toscana	C2
56.1	Umbria	C1
44.2	Marche	C2
49.1	Lazio	C1
54.0	Abruzzo	C1
37.6	Molise	C1
62.1	Campania	C1
47.8	Puglia	C1
53.3	Basilicata	C1
56.7	Calabria	C1
60.6	Sicilia	C1
62.0	Sardegna	C1

Clusterizzazione per valore della Multicronicità e limitazioni gravi. C1>C2.

